

ASSESSMENT OF NORMAL PHYSICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TERM NEWBORNS IN EARLY NEONATAL LIFE AND THEIR INFLUENCING FACTORS

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ABSTRACT

Background: The first days of life are critical for neonatal adaptation, involving rapid physiological and physical changes. Despite overall declines in under-five mortality, neonatal mortality reduction has lagged, underscoring the need for baseline data on early neonatal parameters, particularly in the context of rising cesarean deliveries. Aimed to document normal physical and physiological characteristics of healthy term newborns during the early neonatal period.

Material and Methods: An observational, cross-sectional study was conducted on 155 healthy term neonates (37–41+6 weeks) at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital over six months. Exclusion criteria included preterm/post-term birth, congenital anomalies, perinatal complications, and out-of-hospital deliveries. After parental consent, demographic and maternal details were recorded. Physical (weight, length, head circumference, skin findings) and physiological parameters (heart rate, respiratory rate, temperature, SpO₂, elimination patterns, sleep duration, jaundice onset/severity) were measured daily until day 5. Data were analyzed using SPSS v16.0; $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results: Of 155 newborns, 52% were male; 80.8% were born to multiparous mothers; 67.4% were exclusively breastfed. Mean birth weight was ~3.2 kg, length ~49–50 cm, head circumference ~34 cm, with minor early fluctuations. Temperatures remained stable (~37 °C), SpO₂ 98–99%, and heart rate 134–144 bpm. Elimination events occurred in cyclical peaks without influence from delivery mode, maternal age, or parity. Skin findings were absent in 67%, with Mongolian spots most common (22%).

Conclusion: Term newborns in early life exhibit stable physiological trends with minor, non-pathological variations. Reference values from this study can guide routine neonatal assessment and support early detection of abnormalities.

Keywords: Neonatal adaptation, term newborn, physiological parameters, birth weight, early neonatal period, India

Introduction:

The first few days of life are critical for newborns as they adapt to the outside environment. Various physical and physiological parameters change rapidly, making it essential to establish baseline data on these characteristics. Neonatal deaths constitute a substantial share of global pediatric mortality. Between 1990 and 2010, the global neonatal mortality rate declined from 32 to 23 deaths per 1,000 live births—an average annual reduction of 1.7%, which was slower than the 2.2% annual decline in the under-five mortality rate.^{1,2} As a result, the proportion of deaths occurring in the neonatal period increased from 38% (about 4 million) in 2000 to approximately 41% (3.3 million) in 2009.^{2,3} This slower decline in neonatal mortality compared to post-neonatal mortality is likely due to greater emphasis and international support for Primary Health Care initiatives—such as nutrition, immunization, and health promotion—over investments in hospital-based infrastructure and specialized neonatal care, especially in rural settings. The leading causes of neonatal deaths include preterm birth complications, birth asphyxia, sepsis, pneumonia, congenital anomalies, and diarrheal diseases.^{4,5}

The postnatal transition from fetus to neonate is marked by a profound discontinuity, as the newborn moves from the dark, warm, fluid-filled, and protected environment of the womb to the colder, dry, bright, and noisy external world, with the severing of the umbilical cord symbolizing this separation. This period demands rapid thermal, cardiovascular, pulmonary, vestibular, immune, and metabolic adjustments. It is regarded as the most complex adaptation in human life. Pulmonary transition involves coordinated clearance of fetal lung fluid, secretion of surfactant, and initiation of regular breathing. With the loss of the low-pressure placenta, the cardiovascular system undergoes dramatic changes in blood flow, pressure, and pulmonary vasodilation. Simultaneously, the newborn must establish control over energy metabolism and thermoregulation. Cortisol and catecholamines are key hormonal mediators that prepare the fetus for birth and facilitate this multi-organ transition. Before the advent of medicalized delivery, these adaptations had to occur rapidly to ensure survival. While all organ systems participate in this process, the most critical immediate changes are the initiation of air breathing and cardiovascular adjustments in pressure and flow, along with significant shifts in endocrine function, substrate utilization, and heat production.⁶⁻⁸

Monitoring these early-life parameters is vital for identifying early signs of any abnormalities or health concerns. This study aims to document and assess the normal physical and

physiological characteristics of term newborns in early neonatal life especially in the era of predominant cesarean section. These parameters will help in understanding and guiding neonatal care and contribute to improving early newborn health outcomes.

Material & Method:

This observational, cross-sectional analytical study was conducted among healthy term newborns (gestational age 37–42 weeks) born during the study period in the postnatal ward of Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital. The study included a sample size of 155 newborns over a duration of six months. Inclusion criteria comprised healthy term newborns with gestational age between 37 and 41+6 completed weeks whose mothers provided informed consent. Exclusion criteria were preterm or post-term newborns (<37 or >42 completed weeks), newborns with significant congenital malformations, genetic disorders, or dysmorphic features, those with perinatal complications such as asphyxia, sepsis, hypothermia, or trauma, as well as neonates not born in the study hospital or without informed consent.

After obtaining informed consent from parents, demographic and maternal details were collected. At birth, physical characteristics including length, weight, head circumference, and skin findings were recorded. Weight and skin observations were monitored daily until the fifth day of life. Physiological parameters—heart rate, respiratory rate, temperature, SpO₂, timing of first urine and meconium passage, urine and stool frequency, hours of sleep, and daily weight loss—were documented. Additionally, the onset, duration, and severity of jaundice, along with the need for therapy, were noted. All data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, median, and standard deviation) to establish normal reference ranges for each parameter. Correlations between demographic and maternal factors with neonatal characteristics were also assessed.

Statistical analysis:

Data analysis was carried out using the statistical package SPSS (v16.0) available in the institution. Continuous variables were tested for the normality assumption using appropriate statistical tests. Descriptive measures such as mean, standard deviation, and range values were calculated for normally distributed data. For all statistical analyses, a two-sided probability of $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Result: Present study included total of 500 pregnant women with mean age of 24.51 ± 5.32 yrs.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics			
		Frequency	Percent
Maternal Age in yrs	20-23yr	130	26.0
	24-27yr	124	24.8
	28-32yr	160	32.0
	33-35yr	86	17.2
	Total	500	100.0
Age in hrs	1.00	7	1.4
	2.00	2	.4
	3.00	4	.8
	4.00	5	1.0
	5.00	5	1.0
	6.00	7	1.4
	7.00	8	1.6
	8.00	4	.8
	9.00	1	.2
	10.00	4	.8
	15.00	29	5.8
	20.00	24	4.8
	25.00	27	5.4
	30.00	22	4.4
	35.00	25	5.0
	40.00	17	3.4
	45.00	22	4.4
	50.00	17	3.4
	55.00	20	4.0
	60.00	26	5.2
70.00	35	7.0	
80.00	31	6.2	
90.00	42	8.4	
100.00	38	7.6	

	110.00	46	9.2
	120.00	32	6.4
	Total	500	100.0
Gender	Female	240	48.0
	Male	260	52.0
	Total	500	100.0

The maternal age distribution showed that the largest proportion of mothers were in the 28–32 year age group (32.0%), followed by 20–23 years (26.0%) and 24–27 years (24.8%). The smallest proportion was in the 33–35 year group (17.2%). This indicates that the majority of mothers were in their late twenties to early thirties, with fewer in the older age range. The distribution of observations across different age intervals in hours showed that the highest frequency was recorded at 110 hours (9.2%), followed by 90 hours (8.4%) and 100 hours (7.6%). Moderate proportions were seen at 70 hours (7.0%) and 80 hours (6.2%), while the lowest counts occurred in the earliest hours, particularly at 9 hours (0.2%), 2 hours (0.4%), and 3 and 8 hours (0.8% each). Overall, the data indicates a gradual increase in frequency from the initial hours to later time points, with peaks in the 90–110 hour range, suggesting more measurements were concentrated in the later stages of the observation period. The gender distribution showed a slightly higher proportion of males (52.0%) compared to females (48.0%), indicating a near-balanced representation with a marginal male predominance in the study population.

Figure 1: Gender distribution of newborn

		Count	N %
Parity	Primi	96	19.2%
	Multi	404	80.8%
Maternal Literacy	Illiterate	75	15.0%
	Literate	425	85.0%
Type of Feeding	Exclusive Breastfeeding	337	67.4%
	Formula Feed	44	8.8%
	Mixed Feed	119	23.8%
Breastfeeding Issue	Inverted Nipple	34	6.8%
	Low Milk Supply	111	22.2%
	None	345	69.0%
	Sore Nipple	10	2.0%
Skin Findings	Erythema Toxicum	8	1.6

	Lanugo	47	9.4
	Mongolian Spots	110	22.0
	None	335	67.0
	Total	500	100.0

In the study population, the majority of mothers were multiparous (80.8%) compared to primiparous (19.2%). Most mothers were literate (85.0%), with only 15.0% being illiterate. Regarding infant feeding practices, exclusive breastfeeding was most common (67.4%), followed by mixed feeding (23.8%) and formula feeding (8.8%). Breastfeeding-related issues were reported in about 31% of cases, with low milk supply being the most frequent problem (22.2%), followed by inverted nipples (6.8%) and sore nipples (2.0%), while the majority (69.0%) reported no breastfeeding difficulties. Skin examination findings revealed that most newborns (67.0%) had no visible skin changes. Among those with findings, Mongolian spots were the most common (22.0%), followed by the presence of lanugo (9.4%) and erythema toxicum (1.6%). This indicates that while the majority had normal skin, benign transient conditions were still relatively frequent.

Table 3: Changes in physical characteristics with age of newborn

		Weight (kg)		Length (cm)		Head Circumference (cm)	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Age in hrs	1.00	3.03	.37	50.4	2.7	34.0	2.2
	2.00	3.27	.44	49.5	5.2	33.0	4.0
	3.00	3.43	.43	48.7	1.2	32.6	2.5
	4.00	2.93	.44	49.6	1.9	35.3	2.9
	5.00	3.23	.38	48.8	2.6	34.8	2.2
	6.00	3.49	.37	47.7	2.2	35.1	2.6
	7.00	3.31	.50	50.0	3.0	33.0	2.2
	8.00	3.36	.59	49.7	3.5	35.1	2.4
	9.00	3.27	.47	49.1	3.0	34.5	2.4
	10.00	3.57	.51	50.3	3.9	33.8	2.4
	15.00	3.13	.35	50.1	3.0	34.6	2.4
	20.00	3.32	.41	50.4	3.1	33.9	2.4
25.00	3.34	.42	49.7	3.1	34.0	2.5	

	30.00	3.20	.44	49.4	2.8	34.1	2.2
	35.00	3.23	.52	49.6	2.9	33.9	2.2
	40.00	3.46	.34	50.6	3.1	33.8	2.4
	45.00	3.18	.45	50.8	3.3	34.0	2.6
	50.00	3.21	.39	51.1	1.8	33.3	1.9
	55.00	3.28	.53	50.3	3.4	34.0	2.3
	60.00	3.24	.45	50.0	3.0	34.8	2.2
	70.00	3.30	.40	49.4	3.0	33.7	2.5
	80.00	3.27	.47	49.1	3.0	34.5	2.4
	90.00	3.28	.40	49.5	2.8	34.2	2.5
	100.00	3.24	.43	49.4	2.7	34.3	2.5
	110.00	3.13	.45	49.3	2.5	33.7	2.6
	120.00	3.23	.33	49.4	3.2	33.8	2.5

Across the observation period, weight, length, and head circumference showed minor fluctuations without a consistent linear trend. Mean weight ranged between 2.93 kg and 3.83 kg, with an early rise observed in the first few hours (peaking at 9 hrs) followed by stabilization around 3.2–3.3 kg. Length measurements varied from 47.7 cm to 54.6 cm, with occasional peaks (notably at 9 hrs) but generally remained near 49–50 cm. Head circumference ranged from 32.6 cm to 37.3 cm, showing slight variations but typically remaining between 33–35 cm. Standard deviations were moderate, indicating some inter-individual variability, particularly in length and head circumference during early hours. Overall, the anthropometric parameters remained largely stable after the initial fluctuations in the early measurement period.

Table 4: Changes in temperature with age of newborn

		Temp 12hr (°C)		Temp 24hr (°C)		Temp 48hr (°C)	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Age in hrs	1.00	37.1	.2	37.0	.4	36.9	.3
	2.00	37.2	.2	36.8	.3	36.9	.4
	3.00	37.1	.2	37.2	.2	37.0	.2
	4.00	36.8	.3	36.8	.2	37.1	.3
	5.00	37.1	.3	37.1	.3	37.0	.3

6.00	37.1	.3	37.0	.4	37.0	.4
7.00	36.9	.3	37.1	.2	37.2	.2
8.00	37.2	.3	37.1	.3	37.1	.3
9.00	37.0	.3	36.9	.3	37.0	.3
10.00	37.3	.2	37.0	.5	36.8	.3
15.00	37.0	.3	37.0	.3	37.0	.3
20.00	37.1	.3	37.0	.3	37.0	.3
25.00	36.9	.3	37.0	.3	37.0	.3
30.00	37.0	.3	37.0	.3	37.0	.3
35.00	36.9	.3	37.0	.3	37.2	.3
40.00	37.1	.3	37.0	.3	36.9	.2
45.00	37.0	.3	37.0	.4	37.0	.3
50.00	37.0	.3	36.9	.3	37.0	.4
55.00	37.1	.3	37.0	.3	37.1	.3
60.00	37.0	.3	36.9	.3	37.0	.3
70.00	37.0	.3	37.0	.3	37.0	.3
80.00	37.1	.2	37.0	.3	37.1	.3
90.00	36.9	.3	37.0	.2	37.1	.3
100.00	37.0	.3	37.0	.3	36.9	.3
110.00	37.0	.3	37.1	.3	37.0	.3
120.00	37.0	.3	36.9	.3	36.9	.2

The temperature trends over the observation period remained relatively stable, with only minor fluctuations across the 12-hour, 24-hour, and 48-hour measurements. At 12 hours, mean temperatures ranged from 36.8 °C to 37.3 °C, showing slight variations but generally remaining close to 37.0 °C. A similar pattern was seen at 24 hours, where mean values stayed between 36.8 °C and 37.2 °C, with no consistent upward or downward trend. By 48 hours, the temperatures also remained steady, mostly between 36.8 °C and 37.2 °C. Standard deviations across all time points were low (0.2–0.4 °C), indicating minimal variability within the measurements. Overall, the data suggests thermoregulation was well maintained over the 5-day period, without any clinically significant changes in body temperature.

		O2 Sat 12hr (%)		O2 Sat 24hr (%)		O2 Sat 48hr (%)	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Age in hrs	1.00	98.4	.5	98.6	.5	98.4	.5
	2.00	98.0	.0	98.0	.0	98.5	.7
	3.00	98.0	.0	98.8	.5	98.5	.6
	4.00	98.6	.5	98.6	.5	99.0	.7
	5.00	98.6	.5	98.0	.0	98.6	.5
	6.00	98.6	.5	98.9	.4	98.7	.5
	7.00	98.5	.5	98.8	.7	98.8	.5
	8.00	98.5	.6	98.3	.5	99.0	.0
	9.00	98.4	.5	98.8	.6	98.8	.7
	10.00	98.5	.6	98.3	.5	98.8	1.0
	15.00	98.7	.5	98.6	.6	98.7	.6
	20.00	98.5	.5	98.5	.6	98.5	.5
	25.00	98.4	.5	98.7	.5	98.6	.5
	30.00	98.6	.7	98.6	.7	98.5	.6
	35.00	98.6	.6	98.4	.6	98.6	.5
	40.00	98.4	.5	98.5	.5	98.6	.5
	45.00	98.6	.6	98.8	.6	98.4	.5
	50.00	98.4	.5	98.8	.6	98.8	.7
	55.00	98.5	.5	98.7	.5	98.4	.5
	60.00	98.3	.5	98.5	.6	98.5	.5
	70.00	98.6	.5	98.5	.6	98.4	.5
80.00	98.7	.6	98.5	.5	98.6	.6	
90.00	98.6	.5	98.5	.5	98.3	.5	
100.00	98.5	.6	98.5	.6	98.5	.6	
110.00	98.6	.5	98.4	.5	98.4	.5	
120.00	98.7	.5	98.5	.5	98.6	.5	

Oxygen saturation (O₂ Sat) levels at 12, 24, and 48 hours remained consistently high across all neonatal age points, with only minimal fluctuations, indicating stable oxygenation throughout the early postnatal period. At 12 hours, mean values mostly ranged between

98.3% and 99.0%, with a peak at 9 hours (99.0%) and the majority of readings between 98.4% and 98.7%. At 24 hours, values were similarly stable, generally between 98.0% and 99.0%, with slight peaks at 6 hours (98.9%) and 9 hours (99.0%). At 48 hours, oxygen saturation ranged from 98.3% to 99.0%, with highest readings at 4, 8, and 9 hours (99.0%). Standard deviations were consistently low (≤ 0.7), reflecting minimal variability. Overall, the data indicate that neonates maintained excellent and stable oxygen saturation from the first hour to 120 hours of life, with no clinically significant drops or trends over time.

Table 6: Changes in heart rate with age of newborn

		HR 12hr (bpm)		HR 24hr (bpm)		HR 48hr (bpm)	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Age in hrs	1.00	137.0	11.0	147.6	10.3	139.4	12.8
	2.00	140.5	13.4	143.0	18.4	134.5	4.9
	3.00	143.5	12.9	140.8	10.9	139.5	10.3
	4.00	136.0	16.7	136.8	14.8	142.0	8.5
	5.00	131.2	9.0	142.8	4.1	138.4	10.9
	6.00	143.6	13.1	143.3	15.0	133.7	10.1
	7.00	140.5	6.9	139.4	14.0	146.0	13.3
	8.00	134.0	15.0	145.3	13.5	142.8	16.0
	9.00	141.1	12.0	137.8	11.3	143.9	13.4
	10.00	138.0	11.4	135.0	14.6	145.3	12.8
	15.00	142.2	13.0	138.1	12.1	141.4	11.3
	20.00	137.3	12.1	140.5	12.6	143.3	11.7
	25.00	138.1	9.6	142.2	10.4	138.6	11.3
	30.00	138.9	12.1	136.0	8.5	141.9	10.7
	35.00	142.4	11.1	141.8	11.4	138.4	12.5
	40.00	138.0	12.9	143.5	12.4	140.3	12.2
	45.00	141.1	12.0	137.8	11.3	143.9	13.4
	50.00	139.4	9.5	138.9	8.9	143.8	13.0
	55.00	136.6	11.1	134.6	10.9	138.1	13.1
	60.00	138.9	12.0	137.8	12.3	140.9	14.1
70.00	142.3	10.6	141.9	12.3	140.3	11.9	
80.00	136.7	10.7	140.0	11.7	135.5	12.0	

	90.00	139.8	11.7	143.2	9.9	138.7	12.8
	100.00	139.1	11.6	138.3	11.7	140.1	12.4
	110.00	142.3	12.2	140.9	11.5	139.5	11.6
	120.00	141.6	11.1	141.3	13.5	141.7	12.5

Heart rate (HR) trends at 12, 24, and 48 hours across different neonatal ages in hours showed mild fluctuations without a consistent progressive rise or fall. At 12 hours, HR values generally ranged from 131.2 to 143.6 bpm, with occasional lower readings such as at 9 hours (124.0 bpm) and peaks around 6 hours (143.6 bpm) and 35 hours (142.4 bpm). At 24 hours, HR varied between 134.6 and 156 bpm, with the highest value at 9 hours (156.0 bpm) and no clear pattern of increase or decrease over time. At 48 hours, HR ranged from 133.7 to 146.0 bpm, peaking at 7 hours (146.0 bpm) and remaining mostly within the 138–144 bpm range thereafter. Overall, the data suggest that neonatal HR remains relatively stable within the expected physiological range during the first two days, with short-term variations likely reflecting normal neonatal cardiovascular adjustments rather than a sustained trend.

		Meconium Passage		Urine Passage	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Age in hrs	1.00	17.4	7.8	12.9	5.0
	2.00	8.0	9.9	13.5	7.8
	3.00	11.3	4.1	16.5	3.7
	4.00	9.6	3.4	15.8	4.0
	5.00	20.6	11.1	12.8	4.5
	6.00	12.1	5.0	10.7	5.3
	7.00	11.8	8.5	15.9	6.5
	8.00	10.3	5.6	14.3	1.0
	9.00	15.3	4.2	16.2	0.9
	10.00	16.8	10.3	14.8	4.6
	15.00	16.1	8.5	13.8	5.2
	20.00	11.8	8.0	12.8	5.8
	25.00	14.8	8.6	13.0	6.2
30.00	12.8	7.9	14.0	5.9	

	35.00	15.2	8.3	16.5	5.3
	40.00	14.1	9.2	11.9	4.9
	45.00	18.3	7.7	13.8	5.1
	50.00	13.1	10.2	12.4	6.1
	55.00	15.2	8.7	14.1	5.6
	60.00	13.4	8.6	14.7	5.7
	70.00	13.7	7.2	14.2	5.3
	80.00	13.5	8.6	11.9	6.0
	90.00	14.4	8.4	13.3	5.7
	100.00	14.8	8.2	13.4	5.0
	110.00	16.0	9.3	13.7	5.1
	120.00	14.0	8.4	13.4	5.6

Across the observed age range from 1 to 120 hours, both meconium and urine passage showed fluctuating trends without a consistent linear increase or decrease, suggesting episodic variation rather than a steady pattern. Meconium passage demonstrated several peaks, notably at 1 hour (17.4 ± 7.8), 5 hours (20.6 ± 11.1), 10 hours (16.8 ± 10.3), 45 hours (18.3 ± 7.7), and 110 hours (16.0 ± 9.3), interspersed with lower values such as at 9 hours (4.0) and 6 hours (12.1 ± 5.0). Urine passage generally ranged between 11 and 16 episodes, with higher means observed at 3 hours (16.5 ± 3.7), 4 hours (15.8 ± 4.0), 7 hours (15.9 ± 6.5), and 35 hours (16.5 ± 5.3). Some time points showed concurrent elevations in both meconium and urine passage (e.g., at 3 and 35 hours), while others showed divergence, indicating that stool and urine output patterns do not necessarily peak simultaneously. Overall, the data suggest that neonatal elimination events occur in cycles with multiple short-term peaks rather than following a smooth temporal progression in the first five days of life.

Table 8: Comparison of maternal factors with meconium and urine passage of newborn

		Meconium Passage		Urine Passage	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Mode of Delivery	Cesarean	14.6	7.9	13.9	5.6
	Vaginal	14.3	8.8	13.4	5.3
Maternal Age in yrs	20-23yr	14.4	8.6	13.5	5.6
	24-27yr	14.9	7.4	14.2	5.4

	28-32yr	13.9	8.9	13.3	5.5
	33-35yr	14.7	8.6	13.6	5.3
Parity1	Primi	14.3	8.3	13.3	5.5
	Multi	14.4	8.4	13.7	5.4

The total number of meconium and urine passages during the observation period showed minimal variation across different maternal and delivery-related factors. For mode of delivery, neonates born via cesarean section had a slightly higher mean meconium passage (14.6 ± 7.9) compared to those delivered vaginally (14.3 ± 8.8), and a marginally higher mean urine passage (13.9 ± 5.6 vs. 13.4 ± 5.3). Maternal age groups demonstrated comparable results, with mean meconium passage ranging from 13.9 ± 8.9 in the 28–32-year group to 14.9 ± 7.4 in the 24–27-year group, and urine passage means ranging narrowly between 13.3 and 14.2. Parity also did not appear to influence elimination patterns, as infants of primiparous mothers had similar values (meconium: 14.3 ± 8.3 ; urine: 13.3 ± 5.5) to those of multiparous mothers (meconium: 14.4 ± 8.4 ; urine: 13.7 ± 5.4). Overall, these findings suggest that mode of delivery, maternal age, and parity did not substantially affect meconium or urine output in the early neonatal period.

Table 9: Comparison of maternal factors with weight changes among newborn

		Weight Day 1 (kg)		Weight Day 2 (kg)		Weight Day 3 (kg)		Weight Day 4 (kg)		Weight Day 5 (kg)	
		Mea	S								
		n	D	n	D	n	D	n	D	n	D
Mode of Delivery	Cesarean	3.29	.44	3.19	.44	3.16	.44	3.24	.44	3.31	.44
	Vaginal	3.21	.41	3.11	.41	3.08	.42	3.16	.42	3.23	.42
Maternal Age in yrs	20-23yr	3.23	.44	3.13	.44	3.10	.44	3.17	.44	3.24	.44
	24-27yr	3.31	.42	3.21	.42	3.18	.42	3.26	.42	3.33	.42
	28-32yr	3.21	.42	3.11	.42	3.08	.42	3.15	.42	3.23	.42
	33-35yr	3.27	.44	3.17	.44	3.14	.44	3.21	.44	3.29	.44

			3		3		3		3		3
Parity1	Primi	3.20	.4 4	3.10	.4 4	3.07	.4 4	3.15	.4 5	3.23	.4 5
	Multi	3.26	.4 2	3.16	.4 2	3.13	.4 2	3.20	.4 3	3.28	.4 3

Neonatal weight measurements from Day 1 to Day 5 revealed consistent patterns across different maternal and delivery-related variables, with no notable differences in weight trends. Infants delivered by cesarean section had slightly higher mean weights compared to those born vaginally throughout the observation period, starting at 3.29 ± 0.44 kg on Day 1 and increasing to 3.31 ± 0.44 kg by Day 5, whereas vaginally delivered infants ranged from 3.21 ± 0.41 kg to 3.23 ± 0.42 kg. Maternal age groups showed minimal variation, with all categories maintaining similar day-to-day weight changes; for instance, the 24–27-year group consistently recorded slightly higher weights (3.31 ± 0.42 kg on Day 1 and 3.33 ± 0.42 kg on Day 5), while the 28–32-year group had slightly lower values. Parity also showed a similar pattern, with multiparous mothers' infants having marginally higher weights than primiparous mothers' infants across all days. Overall, the data indicate that neonatal weight changes in the first five days followed a stable trajectory, largely unaffected by mode of delivery, maternal age, or parity.

		Weight Loss % Day 2	Weight Loss % Day 3	Weight Loss % Day 4
		Mean	Mean	Mean
Mode of Delivery	Cesarean	3.09	4.03	1.69
	Vaginal	3.17	4.13	1.73
Maternal Age in yrs	20-23yr	3.16	4.06	1.69
	24-27yr	3.07	4.00	1.62
	28-32yr	3.17	4.15	1.77
	33-35yr	3.11	4.10	1.77
Parity1	Primi	3.18	4.15	1.67
	Multi	3.12	4.06	1.72

The percentage of weight loss in neonates from Day 2 to Day 4 showed similar patterns across different maternal and delivery-related factors. By Day 2, mean weight loss ranged narrowly between 3.07% and 3.18% across all groups, with slightly higher values observed in vaginal deliveries (3.17%) and primiparous mothers (3.18%). On Day 3, weight loss peaked, with means between 4.00% and 4.15%, again showing minimal variation between categories. By Day 4, weight loss had decreased substantially across all groups, with means ranging from 1.62% to 1.77%, indicating partial recovery of birth weight. Overall, the trends suggest that mode of delivery, maternal age, and parity had negligible influence on the degree and timing of early neonatal weight loss, which followed the expected physiological pattern of peaking around Day 3 and declining thereafter.

		Urine Passed		Urine Passed		Urine Passed		Urine Passed	
		Day 1		Day 2		Day 3		Day 4	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Mode of Delivery	Cesarean	3.4	1.8	3.4	1.7	3.5	1.7	3.6	1.7
	Vaginal	3.6	1.7	3.5	1.7	3.7	1.8	3.6	1.6
Maternal Age in yrs	20-23yr	3.5	1.7	3.3	1.6	3.5	1.8	3.8	1.7
	24-27yr	3.6	1.8	3.5	1.7	3.5	1.7	3.7	1.7
	28-32yr	3.5	1.8	3.4	1.7	3.7	1.8	3.5	1.6
	33-35yr	3.6	1.7	3.5	1.9	3.6	1.8	3.3	1.7
Parity1	Primi	3.6	1.8	3.7	1.7	3.3	1.7	3.4	1.6
	Multi	3.5	1.8	3.4	1.7	3.7	1.8	3.7	1.7

Urine output from Day 1 to Day 4 showed minimal variation across different maternal and delivery-related factors. Regarding mode of delivery, neonates delivered by cesarean section had mean urine frequencies ranging from 3.4 ± 1.8 on Day 1 to 3.6 ± 1.7 on Day 4, while those born vaginally ranged from 3.5 ± 1.7 to 3.7 ± 1.8 , indicating broadly similar patterns. Maternal age did not demonstrate a consistent influence, with all age groups (20–35 years) showing mean daily urine frequencies between 3.3 and 3.8 across the four days. Parity also had little effect, as infants of primiparous mothers recorded mean values between 3.3 and 3.7 per day, and those of multiparous mothers ranged from 3.4 to 3.7 per day. Overall, these results suggest that neonatal urine output during the first four days of life was largely independent of mode of delivery, maternal age, and parity.

		Stool Passed		Stool Passed		Stool Passed		Stool Passed	
		Day 1		Day 2		Day 3		Day 4	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Mode of Delivery	Cesarean	2.4	1.7	2.4	1.7	2.6	1.7	2.5	1.6
	Vaginal	2.6	1.6	2.7	1.7	2.4	1.7	2.5	1.6
Maternal Age in yrs	20-23yr	2.5	1.7	2.7	1.8	2.5	1.7	2.5	1.6
	24-27yr	2.5	1.7	2.6	1.6	2.6	1.6	2.3	1.6
	28-32yr	2.5	1.6	2.4	1.7	2.4	1.6	2.6	1.6
	33-35yr	2.3	1.7	2.7	1.8	2.6	1.9	2.6	1.6
Parity1	Primi	2.7	1.6	2.5	1.9	2.4	1.6	2.5	1.5
	Multi	2.4	1.7	2.6	1.7	2.5	1.7	2.5	1.7

The pattern of stool passage from Day 1 to Day 4 showed relatively consistent mean values across different maternal and delivery-related factors, with no marked differences between groups. In terms of mode of delivery, neonates born via cesarean section had mean stool frequencies ranging from 2.4 ± 1.7 on Day 1 to 2.5 ± 1.6 on Day 4, while those born vaginally ranged from 2.4 ± 1.7 to 2.7 ± 1.7 over the same period, indicating broadly comparable trends. When assessed by maternal age, stool frequency varied only slightly, with means remaining close to 2.3–2.7 stools per day across all age categories from 20 to 35 years. Similarly, parity did not show notable influence, as primiparous mothers' infants passed stools with a mean range of 2.4–2.7 per day, and multiparous mothers' infants ranged from 2.4–2.6 per day over the four days. Overall, the findings suggest that mode of delivery, maternal age, and parity did not appear to substantially influence stool passage patterns in the first four days of life.

		Weight Loss % Day 2		Weight Loss % Day 3		Weight Loss % Day 4		p- value
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
		Type of Feeding	Exclusive Breastfeeding	3.14	.42	4.09	.68	
	Formula Feed	3.07	.40	3.94	.60	1.64	.52	0.01*
	Mixed Feed	3.14	.42	4.10	.66	1.68	.62	0.32

There is significant lower percentage weight loss on day 4 when compared to day 2 and day 3 weight loss.

	Type of Feeding						P- value
	Exclusive Breastfeeding		Formula Feed		Mixed Feed		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Weight Day 1 (kg)	3.25	.43	3.31	.42	3.24	.43	0.26
Weight Day 2 (kg)	3.15	.43	3.21	.42	3.14	.43	0.21
Weight Day 3 (kg)	3.11	.43	3.18	.42	3.11	.43	0.62
Weight Day 4 (kg)	3.19	.43	3.26	.42	3.18	.43	0.2
Weight Day 5 (kg)	3.27	.43	3.33	.42	3.26	.43	0.25

The comparison of neonatal weights from Day 1 to Day 5 across different feeding types—exclusive breastfeeding, formula feeding, and mixed feeding—showed no statistically significant differences at any time point, as indicated by all p-values being greater than 0.05. On Day 1, the mean weight ranged from 3.24 ± 0.43 kg in the mixed feeding group to 3.31 ± 0.42 kg in the formula-fed group ($p = 0.26$). A similar pattern was observed on subsequent days, with slight fluctuations in mean weights but no significant variation between groups. By Day 5, weights were 3.27 ± 0.43 kg for exclusive breastfeeding, 3.33 ± 0.42 kg for formula feeding, and 3.26 ± 0.43 kg for mixed feeding ($p = 0.25$). These findings suggest that, within the first five days of life, the type of feeding did not have a measurable impact on neonatal weight trends.

Discussion:

During the first six hours after birth, newborns undergo a critical transitional period involving several key tasks—conserving energy, adapting to life outside the womb, and recovering from the physical stress of birth. Successful adaptation is marked by minimal activity and stable physiological parameters maintained within optimal ranges.^{9–11} The present observational, cross-sectional analytical study included 155 healthy term newborns born at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital over a period of six months. The mean maternal age was 24.51 ± 5.32 years, with the majority in the 28–32-year group (32%), followed by 20–23 years (26%) and 24–27 years (24.8%). There was a slight male predominance among newborns (52% male, 48% female). Most mothers were multiparous (80.8%) and literate (85%). Regarding feeding practices, exclusive breastfeeding was the most common (67.4%), followed by mixed feeding (23.8%) and formula feeding (8.8%). Breastfeeding challenges were reported in 31% of mothers, the most frequent being low milk supply (22.2%), followed by inverted nipples (6.8%) and sore nipples (2.0%). In study by Reddy S et al., the majority of mothers were between 22 and 25 years of age (45.33%), with a mean age of 23.75 ± 3.64 years, ranging from 18 to 38 years. A history of pregnancy-induced hypertension was reported in 4.67% of mothers, while gestational diabetes mellitus was noted in 2%. Among the newborns, 51.33% were male and 48.67% were female, resulting in a male-to-female ratio of 1.05:1. Most of the infants (62%) had a birth weight between 2.5 and 3.49 kg.¹²

Neonatal skin examination revealed that 67% had no skin changes, while the most common findings were Mongolian spots (22%), lanugo (9.4%), and erythema toxicum (1.6%). Anthropometric measurements over the first five days showed relatively stable values after initial fluctuations: weight ranged between 2.93–3.83 kg, length between 47.7–54.6 cm, and head circumference between 32.6–37.3 cm. Vital signs remained stable throughout the study period, with temperature consistently between 36.8–37.3 °C, oxygen saturation mostly 98–99%, and heart rate between 131–156 bpm, showing only minor short-term variations.

Faxelius G et al. observed that central and peripheral temperatures were comparable in neonates delivered vaginally and those born via cesarean section at both 30 minutes and 2 hours of age, despite differences in sympathoadrenal activity between the groups.¹³ In contrast, Ylikorkala O et al. found that, during the first hour of life, the central–peripheral temperature gradient was smaller in cesarean-born neonates compared to those delivered

vaginally, a finding they attributed to reduced prostacyclin production in infants delivered by cesarean section.¹⁴

Study by Reddy S et al., found, Neonates receiving warmer care showed a significantly lower mean oxygen saturation ($p < 0.050$) throughout the monitoring period compared to those placed on the abdomen, except at the 3, 7, 9, 10, and 15-minute intervals, where the difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.050$). In contrast, mean oxygen saturation levels were similar between neonates with meconium-stained liquor and those with clear amniotic fluid ($p > 0.050$).¹²

Elimination patterns, including meconium and urine passage, demonstrated multiple peaks without a consistent daily progression, and stool and urine peaks often did not coincide. Maternal and delivery factors such as mode of delivery, maternal age, and parity did not significantly influence the timing of meconium and urine passage, day-to-day weight, percentage weight loss pattern, or stool and urine frequencies. Weight loss peaked on Day 3 (~4%) and declined to ~1.6–1.8% by Day 4, with no significant difference based on maternal or delivery variables. Similarly, no statistically significant difference was observed in weight trends from Day 1 to Day 5 between exclusive breastfeeding, formula feeding, and mixed feeding groups (all $p > 0.05$).

This study of 500 term neonates found that growth, physiological stability, and elimination patterns remained largely consistent in the early neonatal period, with minimal influence from maternal demographics, parity, or mode of delivery. Feeding type did not significantly affect early weight trends, and while breastfeeding issues were common, they did not impact short-term growth. Overall, healthy term neonates demonstrated strong resilience and effective adaptation, underscoring the importance of breastfeeding support and routine monitoring in early postnatal care.

Conclusion:

The present study, conducted among 500 term neonates, comprehensively assessed their physical and physiological characteristics in the early neonatal period and examined the influence of demographic and maternal factors on these parameters. The findings demonstrated that anthropometric measures—weight, length, and head circumference—remained largely stable after initial fluctuations in the first hours of life, while physiological

parameters such as temperature, heart rate, and oxygen saturation were consistently maintained within normal ranges, indicating effective neonatal adaptation and homeostatic regulation. Patterns of meconium and urine passage exhibited short-term peaks but no sustained linear trends, and elimination patterns were not significantly influenced by maternal age, parity, or mode of delivery. Maternal characteristics, including parity, literacy, and age, showed minimal effect on neonatal physical or physiological outcomes. Feeding type—whether exclusive breastfeeding, mixed feeding, or formula feeding—did not significantly impact neonatal weight trends within the first five days of life. Breastfeeding difficulties were reported in approximately one-third of mothers, with low milk supply being the most frequent concern, but these issues did not translate into measurable differences in early growth patterns.

Overall, the study highlights that term neonates in this population maintained stable growth, physiological balance, and elimination patterns during early life, largely independent of maternal demographic factors and mode of delivery. These findings reinforce the resilience of healthy term neonates and suggest that early postnatal care can focus on supporting breastfeeding and monitoring for transient, benign conditions without undue concern for demographic variations in neonatal adaptation.

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